

**TRADE RELATIONS AND SLAVERY BETWEEN THE KINGDOM OF
XIVA AND THE STATES OF IRAN**

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Annotation: This article was published on the basis of theoretical and comparative analysis of data recorded in scientifically based literature, archival documents and written sources on the trade relations between Khiva Khanate and the state of Iran and the issues of slavery in Khiva Khanate.

Key words: Muhammad Kozim, V.A. Papazyan, Nadirshah, Shergazikhan, D. Gladishev, N. Muravinlar, S. Gmelin, Mak Gahan.

ТОРГОВЫЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ И РАБСТВО МЕЖДУ

КОРОЛЕВСТВОМ ХИВА И ШТАТАМИ ИРАН

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Аннотация: Данная статья опубликована на основе теоретического и сравнительного анализа данных, зафиксированных в научно-обоснованной литературе, архивных документах и письменных источниках по торговым отношениям Хивинского ханства с государством Иран и вопросам рабства в Хивинском ханстве.

Ключевые слова: Мухаммад Козим, В.А. Папазян, Надиршах,

Шергазихан, Д. Гладышев, Н. Муравинлар, С. Гмелин, Мак Гаан.

Economic and political relations between the Khanate of Khiva and the Iranian state led to intense trade relations even during military conflicts. Silk fabrics made by Khorezm craftsmen were also exported to Iran[1.1983.B.269]. The Iranian merchants themselves, while bringing various goods to Khiva, took Khiva silk in exchange [2.1947.B149]. Historical sources show that among the goods that Khorezm merchants took to the cities of Iran, the amount of various fabrics was significant. The Iranian historian Muhammad Kozim Khiva Khan reported that the trade caravan (XVIII century) sent by Khiva Khan came to the city of Mashhad and sold different kinds of cloth (what kind of cloth is unknown) along with other goods[3.1974.B85]. The information of Khorezm historians about two hundred Khorezm merchants who went to Mashhad (1804) with a lot of cloth and countless different goods ("aqshamayi bisyar va amtai-yi beshumor") is also worthy of attention[4.1982.B224]. It is known that different types of silk and cotton fabrics were made in Iran itself, and even large quantities were produced for foreign trade.

First of all, it should be noted that the silk and other textile centers of Iran were mainly located in its northern and northwestern parts, and this area was mainly in the hands of Armenians, who mediated the trade with Europe.

The main part.

V.A., who dealt with some issues of the history of Iranian trade highways. Papazyan also points out that since the 40s of the 17th century, the main part of the foreign trade of Safavid Iran and all the silk exports were carried out through the caravan routes of Northern Iran, Armenia, Asia Minor and Mesopotamia [5.1986.B16]. In this respect, it can be concluded that the fabrics brought from Khorezm are mainly intended for the markets of the eastern and southeastern regions of Iran. In addition, the mutual internal in Iran. wars, roadblocks, and a

large number of customs offices created difficulties in mutual economic relations between parts of the country.

For example, on November 11, 1585, among the gifts brought by Khiva ambassador Khoja Muhammad to the Russian king Feyodor Ivanovich, there was a valuable Mashhad bow painted in various colors with gold embroidery (19.1932.S.68). This is a proof that Khiva traded with Iran.

According to information, Khiva bought Bukhara yarns, cotton, boiled sheepskin and lambskin in Iran.

According to information, Khiva bought Bukhara yarns, cotton, boiled sheepskin and lambskin in Iran. Indian merchants were very interested in the products of the Khiva Khanate, but in the middle of the 18th century, Indian merchants from Khiva rarely brought Khiva goods to Astrakhan. Because Indians bought these goods from Iran and then brought them to Astrakhan.

It should be noted that Iranian coins were among the goods brought to Russia from Central Asia. For example, in 1749, 14 merchants brought 17 consignments of goods worth 17,896 rubles to Astrakhan via Orenburg, including 3 consignments of goods consisting of 15 pounds of silver weighing 10,532 rubles. 3 lots of silver are the so-called "Abbasid" silver coins of Iran. Central Asian merchants exchanged silver for goods in Orenburg. Silver was accepted in the mints in Moscow from 18 sacks or 691 r. 20 k. per poud (a Russian unit of measure, i.e., a miskoli (measure of weight equal to 4.25 grams)) (20.1990.B.118.).It can be concluded that silver coins were brought to Russia from Khiva Bukhara through Central Asian merchants.

One of the information about the Khanate of Khiva is an article published in 1843 in the magazine "Manufaktur i trgovlya". According to it, it receives metal products: lead, copper, iron, cast iron from Russia, Iran, Kokand and Bukhara. Khiva's goods were transported to Russia, Iran and Bukhara by camels and ships.

So, firstly, the Khanate of Khiva established trade relations with Iranian

dynasties, secondly, Khiva goods were brought to Russia by Indian merchants, and thirdly, Indians acted as mediators in Khiva-Russian trade through Iran.

According to P. Nebolsin, Khiva traded with Iran and Bukhara in the middle of the 19th century. Chit wraps with 11-12 vershok (length measurement equal to 4.4 cm, i.e. 48.4-52.8 cm) with small flowers and large bouquets with green edges are presented. One piece of such chits is sold for 1.5 to 2 gold. In exchange for these goods, Khiva will export coins, Russian and local leather, Russian wool, Khiva silk, sesame and other goods to Iran. Green tea was brought to Khiva from Kashgar via Kokan [17.1980.B185]. In addition, the Turkmen bordering Iran produced horses, camels, sheep, carpets, salt, and oil, instead of which weapons, wood, gunpowder, tobacco, dyes, and fruits were brought from Iran. [17.1980.B34].

In addition, dry fruits are imported from Iran. Raisins and raisins are imported from Mashhad and used in making vodka. A pound of Iranian raisins costs 16 tangas (8 rubles).

In 1840, Gilmersen noted in his article that Khiva's troops were armed with swords, spears, and rifles, their commanders wore armor, and armor was brought from Iran. (18. 1840. S. 105)

"Record showing how much duty is charged on what and where in Iran" To transport goods from Tabriz to Resht, you have to go through 6 customs offices, and on the way from Resht to Isfahan, you have to pass through 8 customs offices, and you have to pay duty at each one. gives an idea of the condition of merchants[6.1997.B84-85]. The researcher, who showed that the officials responsible for the transportation of goods abused their official duties, also stated that the merchants were more worried about the merchants than the robbers in the territory of the Safavid state. emphasizes [5.1986.B23].

Information from the 1823 issue of "Sibirsky Vestnik" mentions that silk, semi-silk and thread fabrics, canvas, velvet, gray, etc., produced in Khiva for

coats, and their prices, especially silk fabrics, were not high. [7.1823.B14]. Cloak making in Khiva is very well established, the cloaks of this place are distinguished by their quality and appearance from those of other regions and are considered famous in the neighboring regions.

Khiva's silk and cotton robes, intended for the domestic needs of the population, also had their customers among the steppe population. The Russian merchant Abrasimov, who exchanged such furs for his last goods in the Khiva market, noted that he successfully sold them to the people of the steppe on his way back from Khiva and made a big profit[8.1952.B370].

Cotton kalavas, as well as cotton and silk fabrics, black leather (merlushka), gold, silver and various precious stones were brought from Central Asia to the Kazakh lands [9.1997.B157]. Mac Gahan observed a Kazakh man he saw among the crowds in the Khiva bazaar, "he probably traveled 30-40 miles, sold a pair of sheep, and in exchange for some tea, sugar, some new clothes, and his wife and came to buy some beads-jewelry for his daughter"[10.1880.B406].

Central Asian merchants brought to Iran products from other countries such as tea, paper, "Russian leather", chits, scarves, movut, mirrors, crystal, porcelain, iron and copper dishes, pots, iron and chests, as well as , Russian and those who re-exported (re-exported) their minted cash coins[1.1983.B.269].

Iranian merchants who brought various goods to Khiva took Khiva and Russian coins minted from here, as well as large quantities of Russian goods such as leather and leather[2.1947.B149].

But through other sources it is possible to learn about the Turkmens who were very active in trade with Khorezm and Iran. In particular, in "Shajarayi Turk", although detailed information is not given, it is mentioned about three clans (Ali Eli, Khizr Eli and Tevachi) farming on the banks of the Amudarya, as well as Taka Turkmen traders [11.1999.B128]. There is also information about the Turkmen tribes who stopped the constant attacks and started coming to Marv for

trade and peaceful purposes due to the measures taken by Nadirshah, who sought to revive the economic life in Iran[6.1997.B298].

S. Gmelin, who was on the eastern shores of the Caspian Sea in 1773, reported that the Turkmens traded with all their neighbors: Khivas, Bukharas, Kazakhs, Karakalpaks, Astrobods, and Russians[12.1958.B207]. In addition, the Turkmens, who had a very intense trade with Astrobad and Mozandaran, brought goods needed by the Persians in their boats: oil, salt, animal skins (clothes), sheets, woolen bags, carpets, camel wool fabrics, Bukhara gauzes. , took away saddles, silverware, etc., and recorded that they brought back flour, rice, European gold, silk and cotton fabrics, Iranian money, swords, daggers, and other weapons.

Thoroughbred horses were also delivered to Khiva by the Turkmens. N. Muravyov, who expressed a negative opinion above, also informed that although there are excellent horses in Khiva, the best horses are brought by Turkmens from Gurgon and Atrok.

It is said that the Yovmut Turkmen tribe took an active part in trade relations between Khiva and Astrobad, and Tekke Turkmen tribes took part in the trade between Mashhad and Bukhara through the desert. Slaves, horses, camels, sheep, carpets and felt were taken from desert regions to Khiva and from there to Bukhara. Slaves were sold only for money, and the rest were bartered. From Khiva and Bukhara, grain, lamb skins, Russian metal goods, and yarn were exported to the Turkmen tribes (21.1873.B.34).

In 1851, under the leadership of Rizaqulikhan Lolaboshi, ambassadors from Iran visited. The main goal of the embassy mission is to achieve the release of all Iranian citizens imprisoned in the khanate, to bring them with them to Iran, and to force the khan to issue a special decree aimed at prohibiting organized raids on the borders of Iran, as well as the sale of Muslims, i.e. was to force the abolition of slavery. Unfortunately, as a result of the negotiations, Lolaboshi did not achieve his goal (22.1978.B.16).

The situation of the representatives of the Shia sect was difficult. Because, as a result of Khiva khans or Bukhara emirs marching into Iranian territories, and most importantly, Turkmen tribes' "crowds" - raids, thousands of captives were sold as slaves in the markets of Khiva and Bukhara as Shia - infidels. The state even introduced a special tax exemption label for locksmiths, which further promoted slavery.

In the first book of the second volume of the work "Firdavsu-l-Iqbal", the story of the killing of Sherghazi Khan by Iranian slaves in 1726-1727 is briefly mentioned [13.2019.B155]

The first freeing of slaves in the Khanate of Khiva in large numbers (massively) was done by Shah Nadir Shah of Iran. After conquering Khorezm in 1740, he freed many slaves. For example, in the first book of the second volume of the work "Firdavs-ul-Iqbal", these events are described in this way: "The king spent three more days in tawaqf, and with usaroikim, shar'i sharif, he was in rikqiyat (slavery, captivity) in the land of Khorezm, zakuran and inasan (man) and women) took them all and gave each one to his hash and relative. In this way, some Kalmyk and Russian slaves were killed. Among them, there were more than 12,000 invaders from Khurasan and 4,000 Khivaqdin soldiers, he sent them to Khurasan, built a wall in the four farsakhs of Obivard, made Khivaqabad a season, and killed them. immediately killed the captives" [13.2019.B159].

Russian ambassadors D. Gladishev and N. Muravin, who were in Khiva Khanate at the same time, confirm this information in their memoirs [13.1951.B79].

English historian Michael Axworthy said that the reason for Nadirshah's implementation of such an event was that his mother was captured by the Turkmens and sold as a slave to Khiva [15.2006.B52].

On September 19, 1810, during the occupation of Khatikkol rabato (Gurlanda), its governor Orozali Inok with his 5-6 slaves strongly resisted [13.1951.B103].

At the same time, it is mentioned many times in the work that a special army consisting of slaves led by the centurion of Avaz always participated during campaigns against arbitrary beks, Turkmens, Dashti Kipchak Kazakhs, and Iranian territories [13.1951.B109, 276, 326, 345].

The main source of filling the slave markets of the Khiva Khanate was the "crowds" organized by the Turkmen tribes. For example, in the work "Firdavsu-l-Iqbal" in December 1821, Yavmuts marched to Bukhara and brought many captives. According to the registration of these captives, they must have been enslaved [13.1951.B361-362].

"Riyazu-d-dawla" (Gardens of the State) by Ogahi, the son of Muhammad Reza Erniyozbek, reflects the history of Khiva Khanate during the time of Olloquli Khan (1825-1842). In this work, it is shown in a poetic style that the Iranian-Red Army soldiers were defeated during Olloquli Khan's march to Mashhad and that the price of a hundred slaves fell to one penny in the slave market due to the capture of so many prisoners.

A slave to the overflowing couple,

Ugulub prey is also very expensive.

The space of Bolub Bazar military camp,

That not one penny is the price of a hundred slaves [16.2020.B61-62].

As a continuation of this incident, it was noted that a large part of the population, especially women and children, were enslaved during the campaign of Khiva's troops to Gurgon, Khof and Sabzavor regions [16.2020.B64-67-69].

In the work "Riyazu-d-davla" the army of slaves is mentioned many times. So, this army may be a military group composed of red-headed Iranians and Russian gunners[16.2020.B106-108].

Prince Abbas Mirza, the son of the king of Iran, gathered a large army against the invasion campaigns of Khiva khanate and Turkmen tribes and marched to Khurasan and sent his ambassador with a letter to the khan. In this letter, he

emphasized that many people were enslaved as a result of previous looting campaigns, now they should be freed and the relations between the two countries should be strengthened [16.2020.B243].

There is very little information about slaves in Ogahi's work "Gulshani State" about the time of Sayyid Muhammad Khan (1856-1865). For example, he writes only in the details of the incident of the attack of the Iranian Qajar in 1861 (1277 Hijri, in the month of Shawwal) that in the battle near Marv, when the Turkomans defeated the 35 thousand-strong army of Iran's Hamza Mirza and Qavomuddavla, most of the captured soldiers were enslaved. . For example: "Alqissa, after defeating a strong enemy like you, you became proud and proud, and after you became the host of all the afzun and the comparison, you fulfilled the thanks of Hazrat Zuljalal with forgiveness, They made Marv province their home and refuge. And they sent captives in groups to sell to the surrounding regions. And they filled the bazaars of all the Islamic lands," writes Ogahi [17.2019.B199-203].

The main source of filling the slave markets of the Khiva Khanate was the "crowds" organized by the Turkmen tribes. In addition, those captured as a result of military campaigns of the Khans of Khiva were also sold in the slave markets.

"Riyazu-d-dawla" (Gardens of the State) by Muhammad Reza Erniyozbek's son Ogahi depicts the history of the Khiva Khanate during the time of Olloquli Khan (1825-1842). In this work, it is shown in a poetic style that the Iranian Red Army soldiers were defeated during Olloquli Khan's march to Mashhad and that the price of a hundred slaves fell to one penny in the slave market due to the fact that so many prisoners were taken (23. 2020. - B. 61- 62.).

On pages 37-38 of Laffasi's work "Ozodnoma" he also left valuable information on the prices of slaves. In particular, Russian slaves were more expensive than Iranian slaves because they were hard workers. The average price of Russian slaves was 100-200 gold, while the price of Iranian slaves was 60-70 gold. If sold with the family of an Iranian slave, it was sold for 100-150 gold.

In conclusion, we can say that trade has developed in the country of Iran, and in foreign trade, it mainly exported its goods to the Khanate of Khiva. Turkmen tribes also played an important role in the economic relations of these countries. The Turkmens took the handicraft products they produced mainly to Iran and Khiva Khans for sale. The rulers of both countries paid special attention to the development of foreign and domestic trade.

In addition, slaves belonging to Iranian, Turkmen and other nationalities were also sold in the markets of the Khanate of Khiva. In order to save its citizens from slavery, the Iranian government had to exchange embassies with the Khanate of Khiva several times. Slaves in the Khiva Khanate were mostly citizens of neighboring countries captured during military campaigns.

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